

A Comparative Study of Financial Performance of RCPL & SCPL of Gujarat State

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Abstract

Indian economy is agriculture based and large number of its population directly or indirectly connected with farm or farm produces. Cotton is a major crop of Indian agriculture produce. It has generated employability in its various stages from farming to final product in the form of cotton seeds oil, cotton seeds oil cake, cloths etc. Hence, the cotton ginning industry is a link between cotton farmers and textile industries. Cotton ginning industry is also India's one of the major exporters and adds to India's GDP. The researcher felt that a study on their financial performance would help the various stake holders related to it.

Cotton Ginning Industries provide a link between farmers and spinning mills. If cotton ginners will not provide good quality cotton to the spinners then how would they produce good quality of cotton yarn, so the cotton ginning industry plays most important role between farmers and spinning mills.

This paper investigates the financial performance of selected cotton ginning industries of kadi taluka. The researcher selected two cotton ginning industries namely Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd. Secondary data has been collected from visiting industries in person. In secondary data the researcher collected audit report of selected cotton ginning industries. The data was generated from audit reports of the firms for the period of F.Y 2013-14 to 2017-18. This present study based on comparative analysis of financial performance using Ratio Analysis between Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd.

Keywords Financial Performance, Current Ratio, Solvency Ratio, Assets Turnover Ratio, Return on Capital Employed.

Introduction

Financial Performance of any industry refers to the act of performing its financial activity. In other word, financial performance refers to the degree to which financial objectives being or has been accomplished. It is the process of measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms. It is used to measure firm's overall financial health over a given period and can be used to compare similar firms across the industry or to compare industries or sector in aggregation.

The firm itself as well as various interested groups such as managers, shareholders, creditors, tax authorities and other seeks answer to the following important questions:

1. What is the financial position of the firm at a given point of time?
 2. How is the financial performance of the firm over a given period?
These questions may be answered with the help of financial analysis of a firm. Financial analysis involves the use of financial statement. A financial statement is an organized collection of data according to logical and consistent accounting procedures. Its purpose is to convey and understanding of some financial aspect of a business firm. It may show a position at a moment of time as in the case of a Balance Sheet and Statement of Income, or may reveal a series of activities over a given period.
- Aim of study**
1. To know the financial position of the selected cotton ginning industries.
 2. To compare the liquidity of selected cotton ginning industries.
 3. To analyze the strength and weakness of the selected cotton ginning industries.
 4. To study if the funds have been used efficiently by the cotton ginning industries under study.

Review of Literature

W. H. Bever (1966)¹, in his investigation on "Monetary Ratios as Predictors of Failure - Empirical exploration in book keeping - Selected examinations", utilized proportion investigation as a technique for foreseeing ailment. The proportions of bombed firms vary fundamentally from those of the non bombed firms.

C. I. Altman (1968)², in his investigation named "Monetary Ratios Discriminated Analysis and the Prediction of Corporate Bankruptcy," examined 22 monetary proportions to discover the prejudicial factors. The Z score examination chose five significant variables as discriminators, to be specific the proportion between working capital and absolute assets, retained earnings and complete resources, EBIT and all out resources, market estimation of value and book value of all out obligation and deals to add up to resources. The cut off an incentive for the insolvency was determined as 2.675.

V. Srinivasan et.al. (1978)³, in their examination on "The Application of Multiple Regression Analysis to Financial Ratios of Public Enterprises" inferred that gross profit edge influences the profit from money to the biggest degree. The other two decreasing significance are turnover of capital utilized and working capital. The regression coefficient for working capital turnover suggests that as the turnover of working capital builds its commitment to return on capital utilized declines. It shows that the organization has lesser working capital and it ought to be more than what it is now.

L. C. Gupta (1979)⁴, in his investigation named "Monetary Ratio as Forewarning Indicators of Sickness," dissected 41 Indian material organizations. The organizations were classified into 20 wiped out and 21 non-wiped-out organizations. The monetary proportions of the companies, 63 altogether, were taken to test the present force of affliction. Out of 63 monetary ratios two proportions were pronounced as critical. They were procuring before deterioration, interest and duty to deals and working income to deals.

Sampling

Sampling Technique: Convenient sampling technique was used in selecting industries and collecting data with respect to researcher's area of study.

Data Collection: The current study is majorly based on secondary data collected from visiting industries in person.

Period of Study: Period of this research is five years from F.Y. 2013-2014 to 2017-2018 for the two selected cotton ginning industries.

Scope of the Study: The present study "A Comparative Study of Financial Performance of Selected Cotton Ginning Industries" compares the ratios between Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd. The study attempts to find out the liquidity along with current ratio, solvency ratio, assets turnover ratio and return on capital employed of the selected ginning industries. It helps to express the relationship between the selected cotton ginning industries. The analysis is done to suggest the possible solution. The cotton ginning industries financial performance has great importance and relevance not only for their owners but also for stakeholders, creditors, government, tax authorities, state industrial policy maker etc.

Analysis

Analysis is the process of breaking a topic into smaller parts in order to gain a better understanding. It is systematic assessment and evaluation of information, by breaking it into parts to uncover their interrelationship. The main tool of financial statement analysis is financial ratio analysis. Financial ratio analysis is a study of relation between various item and group of item in financial statement.

Here researcher is calculating various ratios to study the financial performance, i.e. current ratio, solvency ratio, assets turnover ratio, and return on capital employed.

Current Ratio-

The current ratio of the selected cotton ginning industries for the selected years of the study is analyzed here:

Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd.

Year	Current Assets	Current Liabilities	Ratio	Trend
2013-14	292.40	250.60	1.17	100.00
2014-15	377393642	59227190	6.37	95.73
2015-16	397722345	61945971	6.42	96.46

2016-17	690192372	219419053	3.15	47.26
2017-18	854879215	192978630	4.43	66.55

(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd.

Year	Current Assets	Current Liabilities	Ratio	Trend
2013-14	116832802	5450030	21.44	100.00
2014-15	114321922	2507563	45.59	212.67
2015-16	135874647	3323148	40.89	190.73
2016-17	163773345	6984053	23.45	109.38
2017-18	239648291	10539297	22.74	106.07

(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Comparative Figures of Current Ratio of RCPL & SCPL

Year	UCI	JOI
2013-14	6.67	21.44
2014-15	6.37	45.59
2015-16	6.42	40.89
2016-17	3.15	23.45
2017-18	4.43	22.74

Inference:

The above table shows the current ratio of RCPL&SCPL, we are able to analyze that the current ratio of both the cotton ginning industries RCPL & SCPL is greater than the ideal ratio of 2:1. In comparison of RCPL & SCPL the current ratio of SCPL is very high compare to RCPL.

Solvency Ratio-

The solvency ratio of the selected cotton ginning industries for the selected years of the study is analyzed here:

Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd.

Year	Total Funds	Outsider's	Total Assets	Ratio	Trend
2013-14	620155227		762249181	0.81	100.00
2014-15	299100341		389608917	0.77	94.78
2015-16	297081500		408752879	0.73	89.73

2016-17	424064873	720425709	0.59	72.67
2017-18	602944510	881668067	0.68	84.43

(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd.

Year	Total Funds	Outsider's	Total Assets	Ratio	Trend
2013-14	91823588		140505442	0.65	100.00
2014-15	81235120		135398571	0.60	74.07
2015-16	89271775		154949285	0.58	71.13
2016-17	104570657		180670294	0.58	71.46
2017-18	163329705		253990233	0.64	79.39

(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Comparative Figures of Solvency Ratio of RCPL&SCPL

Year	RCPL	SCPL
2013-14	0.81	0.65
2014-15	0.77	0.60
2015-16	0.73	0.58
2016-17	0.59	0.58
2017-18	0.68	0.64

Inference:

Looking at the solvency ratio of Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd, we were able to analyze both the cotton ginning industries have a solvency ratio less than 1.0.

Assets Turnover Ratio-

Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd.

Year	Sales	Total Assets	Ratio	Trend
2013-14	3085240320	762249181	4.05	100.00
2014-15	2900188495	389608917	7.44	918.99
2015-16	2470959633	408752879	6.05	746.31
2016-17	2527874863	720425709	3.51	433.19

2017-18	3804761975	881668067	4.32	532.77
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(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd.

Year	Sales	Total Assets	Ratio	Trend
2013-14	755693306	140505442	5.38	100.00
2014-15	550635860	135398571	4.07	502.07
2015-16	385753150	154949285	2.49	307.35
2016-17	464614850	180670294	2.57	317.48
2017-18	498353427	253990233	1.96	242.23

(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Comparative Figures of Assets Turnover Ratio of RCPL&SCPL

Year	UCI	JOI
2013-14	4.05	5.38
2014-15	7.44	4.07
2015-16	6.05	2.49
2016-17	3.51	2.57
2017-18	4.32	1.96

Inference:

Looking at the Assets Turnover Ratio of both Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd, we analyze that for both the industries the assets turnover ratio is greater than one. It is also observed that the assets turnover ratio of Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd. is decreasing every year, which is not satisfactory. Here both the industries utilized all its assets efficiently to generate sales.

Return on Capital Employed Ratio (ROCE)-

Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd.

Year	EBIT	Net Capital Employed	ROCE
2013-14	45593646	649741086	7.02
2014-15	27393582	330381727	8.29
2015-16	23169287	346806908	6.68
2016-17	28155073	501006656	5.62

2017-18	39894690	688689437	5.79
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(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd.

Year	EBIT	Net Capital Employed	ROCE
2013-14	16396205	135055412	12.14
2014-15	19624646	132891008	14.77
2015-16	17434824	151626137	11.50
2016-17	20383753	173686241	11.74
2017-18	24437273	243450936	10.04

(Source of Data: Audit Report of Cotton Ginning Industries 2013-'14 to 2017-'18)

Comparative Figures of Return on Capital Employed of RCPL&SCPL

Year	RCPL	SCPL
2013-14	7.02	12.14
2014-15	8.29	14.77
2015-16	6.68	11.50
2016-17	5.62	11.74
2017-18	5.79	10.04

Inference:

Looking at the Return on Capital Employed for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd, we are able to analyze the ROCE for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. falls between 5.79 to 7.02 and the Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd falls 10.40 to 12.14 and we also see that Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd have higher assets turnover ratio than Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd for the given period of time.

Findings

From the analysis done and the objectives undertaken, I make the following findings:

1. Current Ratios: A current ratio less than 2 indicates that the company is over trading and under capitalizing, whereas higher current ratio indicates under trading and over capitalizing. Here both the cotton ginning industries for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd have a very high current ratio for the given period of time. It shows bad financial planning or presence of idle assets over-capitalization.

2. Solvency Ratio: This ratio is calculated to assess the ability of the firm to meet its long-term liabilities as and when they become due. Solvency ratio discloses the firm's ability to meet the interest costs regularly and long-term indebtedness at maturity. Here we analyze that both the industries for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd have low solvency ratio which is less than one. It clearly shows that the both industries are in danger zone. It could head into a debt trap.

3. Assets Turnover Ratio: Firms which have large assets base will have lower assets turnover. It is clear from analysis that assets turnover ratio of both the industries RCPL&SCPL have higher assets turnover ratio which is more than one. But in comparison to each other for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd have higher assets turnover ratio than for Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd, which indicates that it has better sales in comparison to its assets of given period of time.

4. Return on Capital Employed: Here ROCE of for Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd is more than for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. should consider improving its ROCE. The most obvious way to achieve this is by reducing costs or increasing sales. Selling unwanted or unprofitable assets, paying off debts, etc.

Conclusion The researcher has attempted the research to study and understand the financial performance of two cotton ginning industries namely for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd. The researcher also made an effort to understand and evaluate the liquidity position, efficient use of funds, and study the finance by outsider funds.

The study has highlighted that current ratio of both the industries for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. And Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd are more than the standard norms. Solvency ratio of both the industries are less than one. Assets turnover ratio of for Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd is less than for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd. ROCE of Sahyog Cotton & Oil Pvt. Ltd is more than for Raghuvir Cotex Pvt. Ltd.

Limitation The limitations of the study are as under:

of the Study

1. The proposed research study will be limited for only selected Cotton Ginning Industries. Cotton Ginning Industries may refuse to provide some confidential financial information which may restrict the proposed research study subject to certain limitations.
2. The proposed research study is based on the secondary data taken from Audit Report of the Cotton Ginning Industries the conclusion of the study depends on the accuracy of such data reported by respective industries.
3. Financial performance appraisal is very wide subject but in the proposed research study the researcher will use only techniques which will be most suitable.
4. All the limitations of techniques of financial statement analysis are also applicable to this study.

References

1. www.investopedia.com
2. Helfert Erich A., "Techniques of Financial Analysis" 4th edition, Richard D. Irwin inc., Homewood, Illinois, (1977).
3. Kennedy and McMillan, "Financial Statements: Form Analysis and Interpretation", IV edition Richard D. Irwin inc., Illinois, (1962).
4. KOTHARI C.R. "Research Methodology –"Methods and techniques" WishwaPrakashan, New Delhi, 1997.
5. Kapil Khatter and Dinesh Mathur, "A Comparative Study of Financial Performance using Ratio Analysis between ABB and Rockwell", Volume-5, (2018).
6. G. Bhavani, "A Comparison of Financial Performance Based on Ratio Analysis with special reference to ITC Limited and HUL Limited", Volume 23,(2018).
7. Mathur, Shivam And Aggarwal, Krati (2016), "Financial Analysis Of Automobile Industries: A Comparative Study Of Tata Motors And Maruti Suzuki", International Journal Of Applied Research, 2(9), Pp.533-539.